

DEPARTMENT OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING
UNIVERSITY OF CAPE TOWN

Embedded One-Dimensional Orifice Elements for Slosh Load
Calculations in Volume-Of-Fluid CFD

Presented by

ELRICH BOTHA

Department of Mechanical Engineering, UCT

Supervised by

DR. L.C. MALAN

Department of Mechanical Engineering, UCT

and co-supervised by

PROF. A.G. MALAN

Department of Mechanical Engineering, UCT

A dissertation submitted to the University of Cape Town in fulfilment towards a degree of Master of Science in Engineering on September 27, 2021.

Plagiarism Declaration

I know the meaning of plagiarism and declare that all the work in the document, save for that which is properly acknowledged, is my own. This dissertation has been submitted to the Turnitin module and I confirm that my supervisor has seen my report and any concerns revealed by such have been resolved with my supervisor.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "E. Botha", written in a cursive style. The signature is positioned above a horizontal line.

Elrich Botha

Date: September 27, 2021

Acknowledgements

To Dr. Leon Malan

I would like to express my deepest gratitude and thanks to Dr. Leon Malan. Over the last two years I have had the privilege to work with one of the finest researchers in the country. He has been a true inspiration throughout and has been a tremendous source of support. He was always willing to engage in discussions and has been very patient with me. For your help and guidance, Leon, thank you!

To Prof. Arnaud Malan

I would also like to express warmest thanks to Prof. Arnaud Malan for co-supervising my masters. Over the last three years, I have had the honour of working with one of the brightest minds in the country. He has been patient and supportive and always willing to engage in discussions. For your guidance and valuable discussions, Prof., thank you!

To the InCFD Research Group

I would like to express my thanks to the members of the InCFD Research Group for making me feel welcome. They have been of great support and I appreciate the discussions I have had with them.

Aan my familie

Ek wil dankie sê aan my ouers, Theunis en Lo-Ann, vir al julle ondersteuning en omgee tydens my tyd by UCT. Daar was verskeie kere wat ek wou opgee waar julle my weer moed ingeproat het. Dankie dat julle altyd in my glo. Ek wil ook dankie sê aan my broer, Theunis, vir al die kere wat jy my leiding gegee het in moeilike situasies en ook vir die voorbeeld wat

jy vir my stel. Laastens wil ek dankie sê aan my vrou, Carmen, dat jy altyd in my glo en my ondersteun in alles wat ek wil doen en bereik. Dankie ook dat jy altyd gereed is om te luister oor my werk en saam met my opgewonde word oor klein deurbrake.

This work is based on research supported in part by the National Research Foundation of South Africa (Grant Numbers: 89916). The opinions, findings and conclusions or recommendations expressed is that of the authors alone, and the NRF accepts no liability whatsoever in this regard.

Abstract

Aircraft fuel tanks contain baffle structures with openings or orifices through which fluid can flow. For CFD simulations, fine computational mesh resolutions are often required within the orifices to resolve the flow through these openings with sufficient accuracy for engineering. This work presents a method of replacing the fine computational mesh elements within the openings or orifices with large one-dimensional orifice elements that integrates seamlessly with standard finite volume computational elements with the intended advantage of reducing the overall computational cost. These one-dimensional elements conserve mass and momentum for two-phase flow in incompressible Volume-Of-Fluid CFD. Instead of resolving the momentum diffusion term, they use empirical correlations to account for the losses within the orifices within an accelerating reference frame for both two- and three-dimensional simulations. The one-dimensional orifice elements are developed and validated against analytical and experimental results using the finite volume CFD code ELEMENTAL[®]. Furthermore, these elements are tested in a violent sloshing simulation and compared to full resolution numerical results as well as experimental results. The elements are shown to decrease computational cost by reducing the number of computational elements as well as increasing the simulation time step sizes (due an increase in element sizes).

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Problem Background	1
1.2	Existing Numerical Orifice Flow Models	2
1.2.1	Fully Resolved CFD Models	2
1.2.2	Embedded Orifice Type Models	3
1.3	Research Scope	4
1.4	Summary of Chapters	5
2	Orifice Flow Modelling	6
2.1	Flow Through Orifice Plates in Pipes and Ducts	6
2.2	Flow Losses within Orifices	9
2.2.1	Viscous Losses	10
2.2.2	Entrance Losses	11
2.2.3	Flow Contraction and Expansion Losses	13
2.2.4	Two-Phase Flow Losses	15
2.2.5	Total Two-Phase Losses within Orifices	19
3	Fluid Governing Equations	20
3.1	Conservation Equations in an Inertial Reference Frame	20
3.2	Kinematics of Flow in a Non-Inertial Reference Frame	22
3.3	Conservation Equations in a Non-Inertial Reference Frame	23
3.4	Governing Equations for Accelerating Orifices	24
4	Numerical Method	27
4.1	Numerical Solution Method	27

4.2	Spatial Discretisation of Diffusive Term	29
4.3	Numerical Calculation of Loss Coefficient	30
4.4	VOF Advection for Orifice Elements	31
5	Validation of One-Dimensional Orifice Elements	33
5.1	Plane Poiseuille Flow	33
5.2	Hagen-Poiseuille Flow	36
5.3	Two-Dimensional Reservoir Test Case	39
5.4	Three-Dimensional Reservoir Test Case	41
5.5	Two-phase Interface Test Case	43
6	Violent Slosh Test Case Results	45
6.1	Full Resolution Simulation Results	46
6.2	Results using 1D Orifice Element Model	48
7	Conclusion	57
7.1	Summary	57

List of Figures

1.1	Catalytic converter with monolith substrates (top). Catalytic converter where monolith substrates are removed and pressure jump model is used (bottom).	3
2.1	Schematic of pipe and orifice section showing flow profile and turbulent vortices with the average pressure along the axis of the pipe shown.	7
2.2	Flow through a short orifice (left) and long orifice (right).	9
2.3	Contracting and expanding flow in a long orifice.	10
3.1	Fluid volume in inertial reference frame system.	21
3.2	Reference frame system in which motion of fluid is described.	22
3.3	Fluid volume in a non-inertial reference frame system.	24
3.4	Orifice within non-inertial reference frame system.	25
4.1	Structured mesh with multiple orifice element pairs (left) and unstructured mesh with three orifice element pairs (right).	29
4.2	Nodes in orifice region (x_1 to x_4) with their cell volumes where the \times 's indicate the actual centroid of the cell volume.	32
5.1	Plane Poiseuille flow.	34
5.2	Mesh used in Plane Poiseuille flow test case.	35
5.3	Mesh and velocity profile of Plane Poiseuille flow test case.	35
5.4	Velocity as a function of height at both the full resolution and one-dimensional element region of Plane Poiseuille flow test case.	36
5.5	Hagen Poiseuille flow.	36
5.6	Mesh used in Hagen Poiseuille flow test case.	38

5.7	Velocity contour plot over cross-section of channel of Hagen Poiseuille flow test case.	38
5.8	Velocity as a function of height at both the full resolution and one-dimensional element region of the Hagen Poiseuille flow test case.	39
5.9	2D Reservoir system with two fluids (left) with full resolution mesh (top right) and mesh with 1D elements (bottom right).	40
5.10	Flow rate through channel of 2D reservoir test case.	41
5.11	3D Reservoir system with two fluids (left) with full resolution mesh (top right) and mesh with 1D elements (bottom right).	42
5.12	Flow rate through channel of 3D reservoir test case.	43
5.13	Sharp fluid interface test case.	44
5.14	Fluid interface plot before Fluid 1 (red) travelled through the one-dimensional orifice elements (top). Fluid interface plot after Fluid 1 (red) travelled through the one-dimensional orifice elements with (bottom) and without (middle) the changes to CICSAM.	44
6.1	Cross-section of tank showing position of baffles and pressure sensors of violent slosh test case.	45
6.2	Full resolution computational mesh of violent slosh test case.	46
6.3	Comparison of full resolution numerical and experimental pressure difference, $p_1 - p_2$, of violent slosh test case.	47
6.4	Enlarged comparison of full resolution numerical and experimental pressure difference, $p_1 - p_2$, of violent slosh test case.	47
6.5	Reynolds number of flow in each orifice over time of violent slosh test case.	48
6.6	Computational meshes for one-dimensional orifice element model simulations of violent slosh test case.	49
6.7	Computational meshes around orifices for one-dimensional orifice element model simulations of violent slosh test case.	50
6.8	Comparison of pressure difference, $p_1 - p_2$, of violent slosh test case.	51
6.9	Enlarged comparison of pressure difference, $p_1 - p_2$, of violent slosh test case.	51
6.10	Flow Rate through bottom orifice in violent slosh test case using one-dimensional orifice element model.	52

6.11	Flow Rate through middle orifice in violent slosh test case using one-dimensional orifice element model.	52
6.12	Flow Rate through top orifice in violent slosh test case using one-dimensional orifice element model.	53
6.13	Mass of fluid on left half of tank of violent slosh test case.	53
6.14	Relative mass difference in left-hand side of tank of one-dimensional orifice element model simulation to full resolution simulation of violent slosh test case.	54
6.15	Free surface of at time $\frac{t}{t_{max}} = 0.2$ on the full resolution mesh (top) and Mesh C (bottom) of violent slosh test case.	55

List of Tables

2.1	Values of B in the Baroczy-Chisolm Method.	17
6.1	Number of one-dimensional orifice elements in each computational mesh. . .	48
6.2	Comparison of computational cost of full resolution and one-dimensional element model simulations of violent slosh test case.	56

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Problem Background

In fluid dynamics, slosh refers to the movement of two fluids, e.g. a liquid and a gas, within a solid structure such as a tank. Common occurrences of slosh are within the fuel tanks of passenger vehicles [1], commercial aircraft [2, 3, 4], spacecraft [5, 6] or in tanker vessels transporting liquified natural gas [7]. The resulting slosh forces on tank structures are an important consideration in the structural design of aircraft as well as its influence on aircraft dynamics and control. It has been demonstrated [4] that sloshing can provide a damping effect on excited structures. This is of particular interest on the wing structures of long-haul aircraft in which fuel is stored. Typically, the wingspan of long-haul aircraft range between 30 m to 80 m and the fuel tanks within span over the majority of the wings [8]. The fuel tanks in aircraft wings are typically longer than 10m with a width and height in the order of ~ 1 m and ~ 0.5 m, respectively [9]. Aircraft wings experience large accelerations, $\sim 10g$, that lead to flow velocities inside the fuel tanks up to 30 m/s [10].

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) is a numerical tool used to solve various fluid flow problems in engineering such as slosh dynamics in aircraft fuel tanks [3]. The Finite Volume method [11] is commonly used in CFD codes to solve the governing partial differential equations by applying the principle of conservation over discrete control volumes, often referred to as volume elements or cells in CFD. The Volume-Of-Fluids (VOF) method [12] is used in CFD codes to model free surface problems such as sloshing in fuel tanks. Numerical methods like finite volume CFD with VOF have been used to investigate the damping effect

of fuel slosh on wing structures [3] and compared to experimental data.

Baffle structures divide fuel tanks into various compartments. It can be used to suppress the fuel slosh loads on fuel tanks [13] or as supporting structures for the fuel tank [2]. Baffle structures often have openings, referred to as orifices in this work, that reduce its total weight and allows fluid flow through it [14]. The thickness of baffle structures are generally thin with some baffle thickness's in the order of ~ 5 mm [9]. The orifice cross-sectional areas in baffle structures range from very small (~ 3 mm diameter) to very large ($>10\%$ the cross-section of the baffle structure) [14].

For stability in explicit time integration, the time step sizes in CFD simulations are limited, amongst others, by the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) condition [15]. This stability condition requires the time step size to be proportional to the cell dimension and inversely proportional to the fluid velocity. For explicit discretisation of the viscous diffusion term, the time step size is proportional to the square of the cell dimension and inversely proportional to the dynamic viscosity. Numerical modelling of flow through orifices using CFD often requires fine computational mesh resolutions [16, 17, 18, 19, 20]. Where baffle orifices (or openings) constrict the flow, its velocity increases significantly. The requirement of small cell sizes along with the increase in velocity within orifices lead to an increased number of cells, reduced time step size and therefore a significant increase in computational cost. A brief overview of CFD models that fully resolve flow through orifices as well as existing techniques that address this issue of high computational cost is now presented.

1.2 Existing Numerical Orifice Flow Models

1.2.1 Fully Resolved CFD Models

Flow through an orifice, or jet flow, transitions from laminar to turbulent for Reynolds numbers between 2000 and 5000 [21, 22] and for many applications, the flow through orifices are turbulent. Therefore, turbulence models or Direct Numerical Simulations (DNS) are required to accurately model high Reynolds number flow through orifices. These models are generally computationally expensive, especially at very high Reynolds numbers.

DNS is currently the most accurate method of modelling turbulent flow [23, 24, 25], but comes at a large computational cost. This large computational cost is a result of DNS capturing all of the length scales in turbulent flow, i.e. from the length scale of the flow

geometry down to the length scale of the eddies at which viscous dissipation occurs [25]. It is shown that for orifice flow at Reynolds numbers up to 15 000, the distance between two neighbouring nodes in the computational mesh should be less than $7.4e - 4$ times the orifice diameter [26]. For a two- or three-dimensional computational mesh, this means the cross-section of the orifice should, respectively, have at least 1 350 or $1.3e5$ nodes.

Turbulent models such as LES [27] and RANS [28] are shown to accurately model orifice flow [29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34]. Even though these turbulence models are computationally less expensive, they require fine mesh resolutions [30] leading to small time step sizes. Other numerical models that address this issue are now presented.

1.2.2 Embedded Orifice Type Models

Some numerical models used to model orifice or channel flow do not solve the full set of Navier-Stokes equations, but rather predict the losses within the orifice or pipe. Ozhan [35] developed a subgrid pressure jump model for use in the development of automotive catalytic converters. This model replaces the monolithic substrate found in a catalytic converter, shown in Figure 1.1 [35], with a subgrid model coupled to the full solution of the Navier-Stokes equations in the diffuser and outlet nozzle.

Figure 1.1: Catalytic converter with monolith substrates (top). Catalytic converter where monolith substrates are removed and pressure jump model is used (bottom).

The monolithic substrate are replaced with an infinitesimal thin layer where only transverse velocities are allowed. A pressure jump source term is then added to the Navier-Stokes momentum conservation equation to model the pressure loss in the substrate channels

$$\frac{\partial \rho u_x}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho u_x \mathbf{u}) + \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} - \nabla \cdot \mu \nabla u_x - C(\mathbf{u}) \delta_s \mathbf{n} = \rho a_{bx}, \quad (1.1)$$

where $C(\mathbf{u})$ is a function that gives the magnitude of the pressure jump, δ_s is a Dirac delta function used such that the pressure jump is only applied to the interface where the monolithic substrates subgrid are and \mathbf{n} is the normal to that interface. Due the small diameter of the substrates (< 1 mm), the flow within the substrates are always laminar and the pressure loss source term given by the Hagen-Poiseuille pressure equation. The model proved to increase computational efficiency significantly while still being accurate. The author found that the model could be improved by adding entrance loss effects of the flow within the channels.

Porter [36] improved on this work by resolving the full Navier-Stokes Equations within the inlet section of the monolithic substrate channels while using the pressure jump model for the downstream section (where flow is fully developed). This allows the numerical model to capture the additional losses due developing flow in the monolithic substrate channels.

Three-dimensional spatial CFD elements have also been coupled to one-dimensional network elements [37]. These one-dimensional elements are used to model flow in long tubes while while the three-dimensional elements model the external flow.

The embedded orifice type models mentioned above reduces computational cost significantly with little compromise to the accuracy of the solution. It is however limited to single-phase flow and the computational mesh elements are eliminated rather than replaced with larger elements. In two-phase flow simulations and cases where the dynamics of the fluid flow on the tank is important, it is necessary to replace the fine computational elements with larger elements instead of eliminating them. This is to track the free surface and to account for the mass of the fluid within the orifices as well as the thickness of the baffles. The research scope of this work follows.

1.3 Research Scope

This research aims to develop one-dimensional orifice elements that replace the standard finite volume elements located in the small baffle openings. The one-dimensional orifice

elements will model incompressible two-phase flow in accelerating reference frames while accounting for the free surface of the fluid. The intention is to reduce computational cost, while still modeling the flow to ensure adequate representation of the physics, such as the flow rates through openings and the corresponding pressure differential. These one-dimensional orifice elements will have an additional term in the fluid governing equations containing a loss coefficient, as in the work of Ozhan [35]. The loss coefficient is determined using semi-empirical methods to ensure that flow losses are accounted for. In addition to the work of Ozhan, the one-dimensional orifice elements model flow losses for both single- and two-phase CFD simulations for both laminar and turbulent flow in accelerating reference frames. Furthermore, instead of removing the mesh elements within the orifice completely, larger one-dimensional elements are used to allow the free surface to be tracked within the orifice. The mesh is defined such that one-dimensional elements are located within baffle openings and will not protrude beyond the surface of the baffles.

The development and validation of the one-dimensional orifice elements will be done in the vertex centered finite-volume CFD code `ELEMENTAL`[®] which is currently being developed by the InCFD Research Group at the University of Cape Town.

1.4 Summary of Chapters

In Chapter 2, the physics of two-phase flow through orifices and baffle openings are investigated. The mathematical formulation of the fluid governing equations and specific details on the numerical implementation follow in Chapters 3 and 4, respectively. Several validation tests are performed in Chapter 5, confirming the correct implementation compared to analytical and empirical cases. Chapter 6 describes a violent slosh laboratory experiment in a baffled tank. The experiment is simulated using full resolution CFD as well as the one-dimensional element model and the results are compared to that of the experiment. The accuracy as well as some advantages and disadvantages of the model are reported on. Finally, in Chapter 7, the conclusions and recommendations of this work are outlined.

Chapter 2

Orifice Flow Modelling

In this chapter, a brief background on orifice flow is presented along with existing orifice loss correlations. These correlations are combined to model the flow relevant to the problem in this work.

2.1 Flow Through Orifice Plates in Pipes and Ducts

A vast amount of theory has been developed on orifice plates and the energy loss in a fluid passing through an orifice [38]. The theory is mostly focused on steady flow through orifice plates within tubes and pipes. The fluid on the left hand side of the orifice shown in Figure 2.1 with a specific set of flow properties, such as velocity and pressure, discharges through the orifice into another fluid volume, on the right hand side, with different flow properties. This phenomenon is termed jet flow.

Figure 2.1: Schematic of pipe and orifice section showing flow profile and turbulent vortices with the average pressure along the axis of the pipe shown.

A jet of fluid flowing through an orifice has a slight pressure build-up upstream of the orifice [39] shown in Figure 2.1. As the flow converges while passing through the orifice, the flow velocity increases with the pressure decreasing. The flow reaches maximum convergence, i.e. maximum velocity and minimum pressure, at a point called the vena contracta slightly downstream to the entrance of the orifice. Beyond this point, the fluid diverges resulting in a decrease in the fluid velocity and an increase in the fluid pressure. Turbulent mixing in the shear layer around the exiting jet as well as flow re-attachment occurs downstream of the vena contracta resulting in a large permanent energy loss.

The fluid undergoes a permanent energy loss (and therefore pressure loss) over the orifice due to viscous dissipation in the boundary layer and jet shear layer. Up to the vena contracta, the energy losses are relatively small and only a result of the boundary layer. Experiments, such as that of Archer [40], confirmed that the contracting flow up to the vena contracta is nearly reversible. Turbulent vortices form mainly downstream of the vena contracta as indicated in Figure 2.1. These vortices extract their kinetic energy from the flow stream and form eddies (a rotary or whirling motion of a fluid). Smaller eddies then form by receiving

energy from larger eddies and eventually dissipate due viscous effects. The turbulent vortices downstream of the vena contracta (which can be found within or downstream of the orifice, depending on the flow conditions and orifice geometry) typically account for more than 90% of the overall losses [41]. In this work the orifice elements will be located inside baffle openings and not protrude beyond the surface of the baffles, with the requirement that losses up- and downstream of the orifice are accounted for in standard finite volume elements. The one-dimensional orifice elements will account for the flow losses within the orifices and ensure the correct flow rate through them.

The dimensionless Reynolds number,

$$Re = \frac{\rho u D_H}{\mu}, \quad (2.1)$$

can be used to determine whether jet flow is in the laminar or turbulent flow regime where ρ , u and μ are the density, velocity and dynamic viscosity, respectively, of the fluid and D_H is the hydraulic diameter, given by [42]

$$D_H = \frac{4A}{P_w}, \quad (2.2)$$

where A is the cross-sectional area of the orifice and P_w is the wetted perimeter (the perimeter of the orifice cross-section with which the liquid is in contact with). In the case of single-phase flow, P_w is simply the perimeter. The critical Reynolds number is the value at which flow transitions from laminar to turbulent. It is dependent on the type of boundary geometry through or around which the fluid is flowing and is determined experimentally. Jet flow through an orifice has a critical Reynolds number of 2000, similar to that of pipe flow [21, 22].

The position of the vena contracta of orifice plates depends on the Reynolds number of the flow passing through the orifice as well as inflow duct and orifice geometric features. The vena contracta due flow through a short orifice (Figure 2.2) is positioned a half to full orifice diameter downstream from the entrance to the orifice [43]. Flow through long orifices reach maximum convergence within the orifice and then attaches to the orifice wall. It then exits the orifice where the flow stream suddenly expands. Long orifices are defined such that the length of the orifice is at least 1.4 times its diameter [43, 44]. Since the flow upstream of the vena-contracta is reversible [40], the losses within short orifices with a length to diameter ratio of less than a half can be neglected. In the case where the orifice length to diameter

ratio is between 0.5 and 1.4 (i.e. the flow does not reattach to the wall, but the vena contracta is within the orifice), it is difficult to determine the losses within the orifice since the exact position of the vena contracta is only known for specific orifice geometries under specific flow conditions [33, 45]. Hence, in this work the one-dimensional orifice elements will be restricted to long orifices. A detailed analysis of the flow losses within long orifices now follows.

Figure 2.2: Flow through a short orifice (left) and long orifice (right).

2.2 Flow Losses within Orifices

The pressure loss in one-dimensional flow analyses are generally written in the form [46]

$$\Delta\tilde{p} = C\rho\tilde{u}^2, \quad (2.3)$$

where \tilde{p} and \tilde{u} are the average pressure and velocity over a cross-section normal to the flow direction, ρ is the density of the fluid and C is some coefficient as a function of the flow conditions and boundary geometry.

Figure 2.3 shows contracting and expanding flow within a long orifice. The point x_u is at the inlet to the orifice upstream of the vena contracta, x_c is at the vena contracta and x_d is at the exit to the orifice where the flow is reattached to the orifice wall. The average velocity and pressure over the orifice cross-section is denoted as \tilde{u} and \tilde{p} , respectively, with the subscripts referring to the point where the average velocity or pressure is taken (upstream, downstream or at the vena contracta). Note that the cross-sectional areas $A_u = A_d$ and will both be referred to as the orifice cross-sectional area, A_o . A_c is the cross-sectional area of the vena contracta.

Figure 2.3: Contracting and expanding flow in a long orifice.

The loss coefficient from Equation (2.3) is dependent on the orifice geometry and the flow and fluid properties within the orifice. The effects that contribute to the majority of flow losses through orifices can be placed in four categories. These are viscous losses, entrance losses due to the developing flow, contraction and expansion and losses due to fluid mixing (two-phase flow). These effects are all discussed in the following sections.

2.2.1 Viscous Losses

Analytical and empirical models have been developed to quantify the pressure distribution along a pipe length as well as the velocity profile over a pipe cross-section. These models are developed for a variety of flow conditions and can also be used to determine the viscous losses in long orifices [47, 48, 49, 50].

The Reynolds number is used to determine whether fluid flow in a pipe is in the laminar or turbulent flow regime. The characteristic length of a pipe used to calculate the Reynolds number is its hydraulic diameter and can be calculated using Equation (2.2). Fully developed pipe flow is laminar for Reynolds numbers up to approximately 2000 and turbulent for Reynolds numbers greater than approximately 5000. Pipe flow can switch randomly between laminar and turbulent flow at Reynolds numbers between 2000 and 5000 [21, 22].

For both laminar and turbulent flows, a one-dimensional flow assumption can be made

if the mean velocity is required rather than the specific velocity profile [51]. The energy losses due frictional effects along a pipe is proportional to the velocity in laminar flow and proportional to the velocity squared in turbulent flow [51]. In pipe flow, these energy losses manifests as a pressure loss as well as an increase in temperature. The pressure loss along a length, L , of a pipe due frictional effects in fully developed flow is therefore written in a generic form, assuming isothermal flow, as

$$\Delta p = K_f \frac{L}{D_H} \frac{\rho \tilde{u}^2}{2}, \quad (2.4)$$

where K_f is the dimensionless Darcy Weisbach Friction Factor and L is the length of the pipe section [42]. The Moody Diagram [47] is often used to relate the friction factor to the Reynolds number and surface roughness of the pipe. The friction factor related to a specific problem can also be expressed by various empirical equations such as those of Churchill [48], Cheng [49] and Avci [50].

The same viscous losses apply in long orifices as in pipes. Therefore, these empirical correlations can be used to determine the viscous losses in long orifices. The equation by Avci [50] will be used in this work to determine the friction factor since it is valid over all Reynolds numbers up to 10^8 . Furthermore, a smooth surface will be assumed since the surface roughness of the orifices considered in the test cases of this work are unknown. The empirical equation by Avci [50] for smooth surfaces is given by

$$K_f = \frac{6.4}{(\ln(\frac{1}{Re}))^{2.4}} + \left(\frac{64}{Re} - \frac{6.4}{(\ln(\frac{1}{Re}))^{2.4}} \right) e^{-\left(\frac{Re}{2560}\right)^8}. \quad (2.5)$$

In this work, the viscous pressure differential over orifices are modelled as

$$\Delta p_{visc} = \frac{K_f L}{D_H} \frac{\tilde{\rho} \tilde{u}^2}{2}, \quad (2.6)$$

where L is the distance between the upstream and downstream points x_u and x_d and with K_f and D_H as calculated by Equations (2.5) and (2.2), respectively. Note that since the two-phase effects will be accounted for separately (Section 2.2.4), the wetted perimeter, P_w , in Equation (2.2) is simply the full perimeter of the orifice.

2.2.2 Entrance Losses

Pipe flow is termed fully developed in regions where the velocity profile is uniform over a length of the pipe. At the entrance to a pipe and after obstructions (e.g. orifices, bends, etc.)

the velocity profile is disturbed and the flow is termed developing, meaning that the profile is evolving to match the new geometry through which the fluid passes. The developing flow can be either laminar or turbulent and the losses associated with it can be significant [52]. The entrance length for flow to become fully developed correlates well with the Reynolds number of the flow. The entrance length, L' , for laminar flow is given by the correlation of Chen [53]

$$L' = D_H \left(\frac{0.72}{0.42Re + 1} + 0.061Re \right). \quad (2.7)$$

At higher Reynolds numbers ($Re > 2300$), the entrance length is shown to be [42]

$$L' = 4.4Re^{\frac{1}{6}}D_H. \quad (2.8)$$

Various sources suggest other empirical correlations for the entrance length in circular ducts [54], but Equations (2.7) and (2.8) are the most common empirical correlations for the entrance length of laminar and turbulent flow, respectively.

Empirical correlations are used to account for the entrance losses, Δp_{ent} , as well. The empirical correlation developed by Chen [53],

$$\Delta p_{ent} = K_i \frac{\rho \tilde{u}^2}{2} \quad (2.9)$$

$$K_i = \begin{cases} 1.2 + \frac{38}{Re}, & \text{if laminar} \\ 0.5 & \text{if turbulent} \end{cases},$$

is often used to determine the entrance losses in circular pipes, where K_i is a dimensionless loss coefficient due entrance losses.

From Equations (2.7) and (2.8), it is clear that the development length to hydraulic diameter ratio is always greater than 15 in turbulent flow, much greater than the length to diameter ratio of the long orifices under consideration in this work. This means that high Reynolds number flow in orifices barely start to develop and the entrance losses are therefore very small. Even though the entrance length to hydraulic diameter ratio can be much smaller ($\frac{L'}{D_H} < 6$) at very low Reynolds number flows ($Re < 100$) for laminar flow, the related developing flow losses at these Reynolds numbers are shown to be negligible compared to the viscous losses [55]. Therefore, in this work the entrance losses within the orifices will not be accounted for.

2.2.3 Flow Contraction and Expansion Losses

As discussed in Section 2.1, the energy loss in an orifice due the contracting flow up to the vena contracta is negligible. There is however a pressure differential due the flow contracting, and therefore accelerating, from the orifice inlet to the vena contracta. In the case of flow through long orifices, the flow expands within the orifice, after the vena contracta, causing a pressure differential due deceleration as well as viscous dissipation. Both the pressure differential due contraction and expansion are accounted for to accurate model the flow losses due the expansion within the orifice.

The change in pressure up to the vena contracta due the flow contracting, and therefore accelerating, is first considered. The energy flux equation [56, 42], assuming steady state, constant enthalpy and zero acceleration is given as

$$\oint_A \left(p + \frac{\rho \|\mathbf{u}\|^2}{2} \right) (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) dA = 0, \quad (2.10)$$

where \mathbf{n} is the outward pointing unit normal vector to the control volume surface, \mathbf{u} is the velocity of the flow and A is the area. Since the contracting flow in orifices are reversible [40, 51, 46], Equation (2.10), which does not include any loss terms, is used to determine the pressure difference due contraction, Δp_{cont} , from x_u to x_c bounded by the control volume with surfaces A_o and A_c (Figure 2.3) such that

$$\Delta p_{cont} = K_{cont} \frac{\tilde{\rho}_u \tilde{u}^2}{2}, \quad (2.11)$$

$$K_{cont} = \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_c^2} - 1 \right) \quad (2.12)$$

and

$$\sigma_c = \frac{A_c}{A_o}, \quad (2.13)$$

where $\tilde{\rho}_u$ is the average fluid density within the orifice, upstream of the vena contracta and σ_c is the contraction coefficient which is determined experimentally.

The change in pressure from the vena contracta to the orifice exit is now considered. The steady state momentum flux equation, excluding shear stress,

$$\oint_A -p \left(\frac{\mathbf{u}}{\|\mathbf{u}\|} \cdot \mathbf{n} \right) dA = \oint_A \rho \|\mathbf{u}\|^2 \left(\frac{\mathbf{u}}{\|\mathbf{u}\|} \cdot \mathbf{n} \right) dA, \quad (2.14)$$

is used to determine the pressure difference due expansion, Δp_{exp} , from x_c to x_d bounded by the control volume with surfaces A_c and A_d (Figure 2.3) since the expansion is irreversible [42, 51] such that

$$\Delta p_{exp} = K_{exp} \frac{\tilde{\rho}_d \tilde{u}^2}{2} \quad (2.15)$$

and

$$K_{exp} = \left(2 - \frac{2}{\sigma_c} \right), \quad (2.16)$$

where $\tilde{\rho}_d$ is the average fluid density within the orifice, downstream of the vena contracta.

By combining Equations (2.11) and (2.15), the total pressure differential due the combination of contracting and expanding flow is

$$\Delta p_{cont} + \Delta p_{exp} = K_{cont} \frac{\tilde{\rho}_u \tilde{u}^2}{2} + K_{exp} \frac{\tilde{\rho}_d \tilde{u}^2}{2}. \quad (2.17)$$

The contraction coefficient, σ_c , varies for different inflow conditions. Analytical and experimental work have been done to better predict the contraction coefficient. Chisolm [46] suggests the following empirical equation to determine the contraction coefficient for orifices within pipes

$$\sigma_c = \frac{1}{0.639(1 - \sigma^{-1})^{\frac{1}{2}} + 1}, \quad (2.18)$$

where σ is the ratio of upstream cross-section to orifice cross-section. In the case where σ is large, such as an orifice on a 2D plane of infinite cross-section, the contraction coefficient calculated from Equation (2.18) tends to 0.610. This value of σ_c is similar to the analytical result of Milne-Thompson [57] who predicted the minimum contraction coefficient, where σ tends to infinity, using potential flow theory as

$$\sigma_c = \frac{\pi}{\pi + 2} = 0.611. \quad (2.19)$$

Grose [58] showed that the contraction coefficient is nearly independent of the orifice geometry provided the orifice is of a convex shape. Other experiments [59] also showed that the contraction coefficient for orifices close to or on the edge of the plane it is situated on can also be estimated using Equation (2.18). In this work, Equation (2.17) will be used to find the pressure differential due contracting and expanding flow with the contraction coefficient, σ_c , determined by Equation (2.18).

2.2.4 Two-Phase Flow Losses

Additional losses occur due viscous effects on the interface between two different fluids. It is therefore necessary to account for these losses in two-phase flows. Two widely used methods of analysis in one-dimensional two-phase flows is empirical correlations and simple analytical models [51, 46, 60, 61].

The simplest technique for analysing two-phase flow in pipes and orifices is homogeneous flow theory where average values of the fluid properties are determined and the mixture then treated as a single fluid. Homogeneous flow theory, in one-dimensional flow, have been shown to be only valid at gas concentrations of less than 5% [61]. A further restriction of homogeneous flow theory is that both phases in the mixture are assumed to move at the same velocity.

The separated flow model [46, 61] uses empirical correlations to determine the total two-phase losses in pipe and orifice flow. The separated flow model overcomes the restrictions of homogeneous flow theory by taking into account the flow velocities, fluid properties and concentrations of each phase. The model works by first finding the flow losses if a single-phase, either gas or liquid, was to flow by itself through the same pipe or orifice. The single-phase pressure differentials if the gas or liquid flows alone at the corresponding phase in the actual mixture's mass flow rate are denoted as Δp_g and Δp_l , respectively. Similarly, the single-phase pressure differentials if the gas or liquid flows alone at the mixture's mass flow rate are denoted as Δp_{g0} and Δp_{l0} , respectively. A two-phase multiplier, ϕ^2 , corresponding to the type of single-phase pressure differential (Δp_g , Δp_l , Δp_{g0} or Δp_{l0}) is determined from empirical correlations such that the two-phase pressure differential, Δp_{lg} , is

$$\Delta p_{lg} = \phi_g^2 \Delta p_g, \quad (2.20)$$

where the subscript g can be replaced by either l , $g0$ or $l0$, depending on the type of single-phase pressure differential considered. Various empirical correlations to find the two-phase multiplier, using either of the single-phase pressure differentials, exist [46, 61, 62, 63, 64, 51].

Lockhart and Martinelli [62] found correlations to determine the two-phase multipliers, ϕ_l^2 and ϕ_g^2 . These two-phase multipliers are plotted to a base of the Lockhart-Martinelli parameter [62], X ,

$$X^2 = \frac{\phi_g^2}{\phi_l^2} = \frac{\Delta p_l}{\Delta p_g}, \quad (2.21)$$

for various flow conditions. Chisolm [46] developed the C-coefficient method to find the

Lockhart and Martinelli [62] two-phase multipliers without looking up correlations on graphs. Martinelli and Nelson [63] found correlations to determine the two-phase multipliers, ϕ_{l0}^2 or ϕ_{g0}^2 , which are plotted to a base of the concentration of the gas in the mixture. Chisolm and Sutherland [65] defined a physical property coefficient, Γ ,

$$\Gamma^2 = \frac{\Delta p_{g0}}{\Delta p_{l0}}, \quad (2.22)$$

which is used in the development of both the B coefficient method [65] and the Baroczy correlation method [64] to find ϕ_{l0}^2 and ϕ_{g0}^2 . Chisolm [46] combined these two methods to develop the Baroczy-Chisolm method used to find ϕ_{l0}^2 .

Friedel [66] compared a number of two-phase multiplier predictive methods to an experimental data bank with 6406 data points. Of the 14 correlations that he compared, the Baroczy-Chisolm method outperformed the others. The arithmetic mean deviation of the two-phase multiplier ϕ_{l0}^2 were found to be 12%. In this work, the Baroczy-Chisolm method will therefore be used to determine the two-phase multiplier for the viscous losses within orifices.

Baroczy-Chisolm Method for Two-Phase Viscous Losses

Some basic definitions, terminology and dimensionless numbers are essential to understanding the literature on the Baroczy-Chisolm method [46]. The dryness fraction,

$$x = \frac{\rho_g \tilde{u}_g A_g}{\rho_l \tilde{u}_l A_l + \rho_g \tilde{u}_g A_g}, \quad (2.23)$$

is the ratio of the mass flow rate of the gas to the liquid-gas mixture where the subscripts l and g are used to distinguish between the liquid and gas phase, respectively, and A_l and A_g are the areas of the orifice cross-section occupied by the liquid and gas, respectively. The void fraction, ξ , is the ratio between the volume of the orifice occupied by the gas, V_g , to the total volume over a length in the orifice, V_{lg} , such that

$$\xi = \frac{V_g}{V_{lg}}. \quad (2.24)$$

The mass velocity, G , is used extensively in one-dimensional two-phase flow literature and is given as

$$G = \rho_l \tilde{u}_l \frac{1 - \xi}{1 - x} = \rho_g \tilde{u}_g \frac{\xi}{x}. \quad (2.25)$$

The two-phase multiplier, using the Baroczy-Chisolm method, is defined as

$$\phi_{l0}^2 = 1 + (\Gamma^2 - 1)(Bx(1 - x) + x^2), \quad (2.26)$$

where the coefficient B can be found in Table 2.1 [46], the physical property coefficient, Γ , can be determined using Equation (2.22) and Δp_{l0} and Δp_{g0} are found using Equations (2.4) and (2.25) as

$$\Delta p_{l0} = \frac{K_{f10}L}{D_H} \frac{G^2}{2\rho_l} \quad (2.27)$$

and

$$\Delta p_{g0} = \frac{K_{fg0}L}{D_H} \frac{G^2}{2\rho_g}, \quad (2.28)$$

respectively. K_{fg0} and K_{f10} are found using Equation (2.5) and D_H is found using Equation (2.2) where the wetted perimeter, P_w , is the full orifice perimeter. Note that the Reynolds number in Equation (2.5) is determined using the orifice hydraulic diameter, D_H (2.2), (where P_w is again the full perimeter) with the mass velocity of the mixture and the viscosity of the respective phase being dealt with.

Γ	$G \left(\frac{kg}{m^2s} \right)$	B
$\Gamma \leq 9.5$	$G \leq 500$	4.8
	$500 < G < 1900$	$\frac{2400}{G}$
	$G \geq 1900$	$\frac{55}{G^{0.5}}$
$9.5 < \Gamma < 28$	$G \leq 600$	$\frac{520}{\Gamma G^{0.5}}$
	$G > 600$	$\frac{21}{\Gamma}$
$\Gamma \geq 28$		$\frac{15000}{\Gamma^2 G^{0.5}}$

Table 2.1: Values of B in the Baroczy-Chisolm Method.

Finally, the total two-phase viscous pressure differential is calculated, using Equations (2.20), (2.26) and (2.27), as

$$\Delta p_{l0viscTP} = \phi_{l0visc}^2 \Delta p_{l0visc} = \phi_{l0visc}^2 \frac{K_{f10}L}{D_H} \frac{G^2}{2\rho_l}. \quad (2.29)$$

Further research have been conducted to extend the two-phase multiplier to contracting and expanding flow as in the case of orifice flow [46, 51].

Two-Phase Losses for Contracting and Expanding Flow

Chisolm [46] and Kojasoy [51] developed methods to expand the application of two-phase multipliers to obstructions such as orifices in pipes and ducts. These methods are used to only determine the two-phase multiplier for the pressure difference due the contraction and expansion caused by orifices. The two-phase multiplier due the effects of an obstruction such as an orifice is given as [46]

$$\phi_{l0ori}^2 = \left(1 + \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\rho_g} - 1 \right) (B_{ori}x(1-x) + x^2) \right), \quad (2.30)$$

where

$$B_{ori} = \frac{1}{S^n}, \quad (2.31)$$

and the velocity ratio or slip ratio, S , is defined as

$$S = \left(1 + x \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\rho_g} - 1 \right) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (2.32)$$

The coefficient n is determined experimentally. Kojasoy [51] found n to be zero downstream of the vena contracta since the expanding flow is well mixed and 0.15 and 0.4 upstream of the vena contracta for long and short orifices, respectively. The maximum relative error of the two-phase multiplier in Equation (2.30) to that determined by experiments are found to be within 20% [51]. Roul [60] performed a numerical investigation to compare various two-phase multiplier models for orifice flow and found that Equation (2.30) fits well with numerical data.

Finally, in this work, the total two-phase pressure differential due contracting and expanding flow, respectively, are calculated, using Equations (2.20), (2.30), (2.31) and (2.32), as

$$\Delta p_{l0contTP} = \phi_{l0cont}^2 \Delta p_{l0cont} = \left(1 + \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\rho_g} - 1 \right) \left(\frac{1}{S^{0.15}} x(1-x) + x^2 \right) \right) K_{cont} \frac{G^2}{2\rho_l} \quad (2.33)$$

and

$$\Delta p_{l0expTP} = \phi_{l0exp}^2 \Delta p_{l0exp} = \left(1 + \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\rho_g} - 1 \right) (x(1-x) + x^2) \right) K_{exp} \frac{G^2}{2\rho_l}, \quad (2.34)$$

where K_{cont} and K_{exp} are defined in Equations (2.12) and (2.16).

2.2.5 Total Two-Phase Losses within Orifices

The total pressure differential over a long orifice accounting for two-phase flow in this work is determined by adding loss terms in Equations (2.29), (2.33) and (2.34) such that

$$\Delta p_{total} = \phi_{l0visc}^2 \frac{K_{f10}L}{D_H} \frac{G^2}{2\rho_l} + \phi_{l0cont}^2 K_{cont} \frac{G^2}{2\rho_l} + \phi_{l0exp}^2 K_{exp} \frac{G^2}{2\rho_l} = C \frac{G^2}{\rho_l}, \quad (2.35)$$

where

$$C = \frac{\phi_{l0visc}^2 \frac{K_{f10}L}{D_H} + \phi_{l0cont}^2 K_{cont} + \phi_{l0exp}^2 K_{exp}}{2}. \quad (2.36)$$

The calculation of the loss coefficient is implemented in the code `ELEMENTAL`[®]. The governing equations now follow with the numerical implementation of the one-dimensional orifice elements in the chapter thereafter.

Chapter 3

Fluid Governing Equations

In this chapter, the fluid governing equations are presented. It starts off by first looking at the conservation equations in an inertial reference frame. It then follows with a description of kinematics in a non-inertial reference frame to allow the conservation equations to be evolved for such a system. Finally, it deals with the governing equations for flow within accelerating orifices.

3.1 Conservation Equations in an Inertial Reference Frame

The conservation of linear momentum equation can be derived by first considering Newton's Second Law [67]

$$\Sigma \mathbf{F} = \frac{D}{Dt}(m\mathbf{u}) = m\mathbf{a} \quad (3.1)$$

for a fluid volume $V(t)$ shown in Figure 3.3. $V(t)$ is enclosed by a surface $A(t)$ with outward pointing unit normal vector \mathbf{n} . The volume is located in an inertial reference frame (X - Y - Z), contains a fluid with density ρ and is subject to a force, which is divided into a surface force $\mathbf{F}|_A$ and a body force $\mathbf{F}|_V$.

Figure 3.1: Fluid volume in inertial reference frame system.

Equation (3.1) can be re-written as follows

$$\oint_{A(t)} d\mathbf{F}|_A + \int_{V(t)} d\mathbf{F}|_V = \frac{D}{Dt} \int_{V(t)} \rho \mathbf{u}_F dV$$

$$\oint_{A(t)} -p\mathbf{n} + \boldsymbol{\tau}\mathbf{n} dA + \int_{V(t)} \rho \mathbf{g} dV = \frac{D}{Dt} \int_{V(t)} \rho \mathbf{u}_F dV, \quad (3.2)$$

where p is the pressure and \mathbf{g} is the body force acceleration due gravity and is expressed as -9.81 m/s^2 in the positive Y -direction. The viscous shear tensor for incompressible flow, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$, is given as

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \nabla \cdot \mu(\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T), \quad (3.3)$$

where μ is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid. By applying Reynold's Transport Theorem,

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \int_{V(t)} \phi dV = \int_{V(t)} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \phi \mathbf{u} dV, \quad (3.4)$$

where ϕ is a scalar, vector or tensor valued function, the momentum conservation equation (3.2) can finally be written in differential form (also referred to as strong form) as

$$\frac{\partial \rho \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) + \nabla p - \nabla \cdot \mu(\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) = \rho \mathbf{g}, \quad (3.5)$$

The conservation of mass for an incompressible fluid is given by

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0. \quad (3.6)$$

The mass and momentum conservation equations are known as the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations. The kinematics of flow in a non-inertial reference frame is now considered.

3.2 Kinematics of Flow in a Non-Inertial Reference Frame

This work concerns the flow inside fluid containment structures, like aircraft fuel tanks. In the general case the structures may be subject to translational as well as rotational acceleration. The governing equations are thus derived for flow in a non-inertial reference frame. Consider an individual fluid particle at a point F , as shown in Figure 3.2. Point F can move relative to point B , defined as the origin of the non-inertial reference frame, x - y - z . The fluid is contained within a rigid tank in the x - y - z reference frame. This non-inertial reference frame, x - y - z , can rotate and translate relative to point A , defined as the origin of some inertial reference frame, X - Y - Z . Gravitational acceleration is denoted by \mathbf{g} .

Figure 3.2: Reference frame system in which motion of fluid is described.

The position vector, \mathbf{x}_F , describes the position of a fluid particle relative to X - Y - Z . Using vector addition

$$\mathbf{x}_F = \mathbf{x}_B + \mathbf{x}_{F/B}, \quad (3.7)$$

where \mathbf{x}_B is the position of B relative to X - Y - Z and $\mathbf{x}_{F/B}$ is the position of F relative to B . By differentiating the equation with respect to time, the velocity of the fluid particle, \mathbf{u}_F ,

relative to X - Y - Z is [68]

$$\mathbf{u}_F = \mathbf{u}_B + \mathbf{u}_{F/B} + \boldsymbol{\omega}_B \times \mathbf{x}_{F/B}, \quad (3.8)$$

where $\mathbf{u}_{F/B}$ is the velocity of F relative to B , \mathbf{u}_B is the velocity of B relative to X - Y - Z and $\boldsymbol{\omega}_B$ is the rotational velocity of the reference frame x - y - z about B . Taking further time derivatives and excluding the acceleration due gravity, the acceleration of the particle of fluid, \mathbf{a}_F , is

$$\mathbf{a}_F = \mathbf{a}_B + \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_B \times \mathbf{x}_{F/B} + \boldsymbol{\omega}_B \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}_B \times \mathbf{x}_{F/B}) + 2\boldsymbol{\omega}_B \times \mathbf{u}_{F/B} + \mathbf{a}_{F/B}, \quad (3.9)$$

where $\dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_B$ is the angular acceleration of x - y - z about B . The term \mathbf{a}_B describes the linear acceleration of B relative to X - Y - Z . The terms $\dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_B \times \mathbf{x}_{F/B}$ and $\boldsymbol{\omega}_B \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}_B \times \mathbf{x}_{F/B})$ describe, respectively, the tangential and normal component of the acceleration of the fluid particle relative to B due to the angular velocity and angular acceleration of x - y - z . The Coriolis acceleration, $2\boldsymbol{\omega}_B \times \mathbf{u}_{F/B}$, represents the difference in acceleration of the motion of the fluid particle measured relative to the path on the non-inertial reference frame it is travelling along and the inertial reference frame. The term $\mathbf{a}_{F/B}$ describes the acceleration of a fluid particle relative to B . Next, the fluid governing equations in a non-inertial reference frame system, as described in this section, is considered.

3.3 Conservation Equations in a Non-Inertial Reference Frame

The momentum conservation equation (3.5) is now modified for the non-inertial reference frame system described in the aforementioned section. The CFD domain will be located in the non-inertial reference frame and the velocity solved by the code will be $\mathbf{u}_{F/B}$. The fluid volume $V(t)$ in Figure 3.1 is now presented in a non-inertial reference frame system shown in Figure 3.3. From Equation (3.8), \mathbf{u}_F can be substituted into Equation (3.5) such that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \rho \mathbf{u}_{F/B}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}_{F/B} \otimes \mathbf{u}_{F/B}) + \nabla p - \nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) \\ = \rho \mathbf{g} - \rho (\mathbf{a}_B + \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_B \times \mathbf{x}_{F/B} + \boldsymbol{\omega}_B \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}_B \times \mathbf{x}_{F/B}) + \boldsymbol{\omega}_B \times \mathbf{u}_{F/B}) \\ = \rho \mathbf{g} - \rho \mathbf{a}_\Omega = \rho (\mathbf{g} - \mathbf{a}_\Omega), \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

where \mathbf{a}_Ω is acceleration contribution due the motion of the domain and is expressed with respect to the x - y - z coordinate axes. In the case where the domain experiences a rotation, the gravitational acceleration vector, $\mathbf{g} = -9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$ in the Y direction, have to undergo a transformation such that it is expressed with respect to the x - y - z coordinate axes. The following section describes the governing equations within accelerating orifices.

Figure 3.3: Fluid volume in a non-inertial reference frame system.

3.4 Governing Equations for Accelerating Orifices

This section looks at a momentum conservation equation for flow from the entrance to the exit of an orifice in motion. An orifice with diameter d and length L surrounded by a fluid of density ρ is shown in Figure 3.4. The orifice is fixed in the x - y - z reference frame which is subjected to an acceleration \mathbf{a} and rotation $\boldsymbol{\omega}_B$ while the pressures p_1 and p_2 are taken at \mathbf{x}_1 and \mathbf{x}_2 . Unit vector \mathbf{n}_O indicates the 1D direction vector of the flow within the orifice in the x - y - z reference.

Figure 3.4: Orifice within non-inertial reference frame system.

Assuming axial flow within an orifice aligned with the x -axis ($u_y = u_z = 0$), the viscous term in Equation (3.10) can be replaced with a single empirical loss term such that

$$\nabla \cdot \mu(\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) \approx -\frac{C \rho \tilde{u}_O^2}{L} \mathbf{e}_x, \quad (3.11)$$

where \tilde{u}_O is the average flow velocity through the orifice, \mathbf{e}_x is a unit vector in the positive x -direction and C is the loss coefficient as in Equation (2.36). In a more general case where the orifice is not aligned with a specific axis and where the whole fluid domain is considered, Equation (3.11) is modified such that

$$\nabla \cdot \mu(\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) = (\nabla \cdot \mu(\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T)) (1 - H_O) - \frac{C \rho \tilde{u}_O^2}{L} H_O \mathbf{n}_O, \quad (3.12)$$

where \mathbf{n}_O is the unit normal vector along the orifice in the direction of the flow and H_O is a Heaviside function with value 1 within the orifice and 0 elsewhere. Combining Equations (3.12) and (3.5) gives the momentum conservation equation for flow in accelerating

orifices

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \rho \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) + \nabla p - (\nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T)) (1 - H_O) + \frac{C \rho \tilde{u}_O^2}{L} H_O \mathbf{n}_O \\ \approx \rho \mathbf{g} - \rho \mathbf{a}_\Omega. \end{aligned} \quad (3.13)$$

The numerical implementation of the one-dimensional orifice element model now follows.

Chapter 4

Numerical Method

In this chapter the numerical solution method of the governing equations presented in the previous chapter is detailed. This is followed by the novel developments made in the `ELEMENTAL`[®] code for one-dimensional orifice elements. First, the spatial discretisation of the diffusive term for both interior and orifice nodes are discussed. This is followed by a required adjustment to the VOF equation (4.1) to account for large one-dimensional elements.

4.1 Numerical Solution Method

The numerical solution to the fluid governing equations, (3.6) and (3.10), is described here. `ELEMENTAL`[®] uses a vertex centered finite volume method such that the control volumes are formed as a geometric dual to the cells. In the case of two-phase flow, the fluids are assumed immiscible. A one-fluid formulation [69] is used, so that the same set of equations is solved everywhere in the computational domain, regardless of the phase or phases present in the computational cell. To track the phases, we solve the VOF equation:

$$\frac{\partial H_\alpha}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} H_\alpha = 0. \quad (4.1)$$

where H_α is a Heaviside function having the value of 1 in the liquid phase and 0 in the gas phase. The volume fraction or Volume-Of-Fluid, α , is the average value of H_α in a computational cell, V_i , such that

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{V_i} \int_V H_\alpha dV, \quad (4.2)$$

This means that $\alpha = 1$ for a cell completely filled with liquid and $\alpha = 0$ for a cell completely filled with gas. The advection of α , the second term in (4.1), is calculated using the Compressive Interface Capturing Scheme for Arbitrary Meshes (CICSAM) method [70]. The density and viscosity of the fluid in each cell is calculated using an arithmetic average and is given by

$$\rho = \alpha\rho_1 + (1 - \alpha)\rho_0 \quad (4.3)$$

and

$$\mu = \alpha\mu_1 + (1 - \alpha)\mu_0, \quad (4.4)$$

where subscripts 1 and 0 denote the liquid and gas, respectively. The mass and momentum equations, (3.6) and (3.10), is solved using the split projection method [71]

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\rho^{n+1}\mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \rho^{n+1}\mathbf{u}^*}{\Delta t} + \frac{\rho^{n+1}\mathbf{u}^* - \rho^n\mathbf{u}^n}{\Delta t} = & -\nabla p^{n+1} - \nabla \cdot \rho\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}|^n \\ & + \nabla \cdot \mu(\nabla\mathbf{u} + \nabla\mathbf{u}^T)|^n + \rho(\mathbf{g} - \mathbf{a}_\Omega)|^n, \end{aligned} \quad (4.5)$$

so that Equation (4.5) can be split into

$$\frac{\rho^{n+1}\mathbf{u}^* - \rho^n\mathbf{u}^n}{\Delta t} = -\nabla \cdot \rho\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}|^n + \nabla \cdot \mu(\nabla\mathbf{u} + \nabla\mathbf{u}^T)|^n + \rho(\mathbf{g} - \mathbf{a}_\Omega)|^n \quad (4.6)$$

and

$$\frac{\rho^{n+1}\mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \rho^{n+1}\mathbf{u}^*}{\Delta t} = -\nabla p^{n+1}, \quad (4.7)$$

where \mathbf{u}^* is the projected velocity. Equations (4.6) and (4.7) can be rearranged such that

$$\mathbf{u}^* = \left(\frac{1}{\rho^{n+1}} \right) (\rho^n\mathbf{u}^n + \Delta t (-\nabla \cdot \rho\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}|^n + \nabla \cdot \mu(\nabla\mathbf{u} + \nabla\mathbf{u}^T)|^n + \rho(\mathbf{g} - \mathbf{a}_\Omega)|^n)) \quad (4.8)$$

and

$$\mathbf{u}^{n+1} = \mathbf{u}^* - \frac{\Delta t}{\rho^{n+1}} \nabla p^{n+1}. \quad (4.9)$$

Taking the divergence of (4.9) and applying mass conservation (3.6),

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}^{n+1} = 0 = \nabla \cdot \left(\mathbf{u}^* - \frac{\Delta t}{\rho^{n+1}} \nabla p^{n+1} \right). \quad (4.10)$$

Equation (4.10) is the Poisson equation and is solved such that its residual is smaller than some user-specified tolerance condition. Equations (4.8) to (4.10) along with the VOF equation (4.1) is solved in ELEMENTAL[®] using a Predictor-Corrector time integration scheme, which provides second order time integration accuracy. The spatial discretisation of the diffusive term is now considered.

4.2 Spatial Discretisation of Diffusive Term

Figure 4.1 shows two-dimensional meshes containing orifice elements: a structured mesh on the left and an unstructured mesh on the right. The control volumes are shown with the dotted lines. Nodes that do not form part of the boundary are termed interior nodes (eg. F , G , H , etc.). The orifice boundary nodes are denoted as O_{C_i} and the internal orifice nodes are denoted as O_{A_i} and O_{B_i} for left and right hand side orifice nodes, respectively. This section deals with the discretisation of the diffusive term for both interior and orifice nodes. Vertex centred finite volume discretisation is used to discretise the term.

Figure 4.1: Structured mesh with multiple orifice element pairs (left) and unstructured mesh with three orifice element pairs (right).

The diffusive term for an interior node, e.g. D , is discretised below

$$\begin{aligned}
 \nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) &= \frac{1}{V_D} \int_{V_D} \nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) dV \\
 &= \frac{1}{V_D} \oint_{A_D} \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) \cdot \mathbf{n} dA \\
 &= \frac{1}{V_D} \sum_{f \in A_D} (\mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) \cdot \mathbf{\Gamma})|_f, \tag{4.11}
 \end{aligned}$$

where V_D is the volume of the cell at node D , A_D is the surface enclosing V_D and the subscript f indicates a specific face of the the area A_D . $\mathbf{\Gamma}$ is the outward pointing normal vector of the face with magnitude equal to the area of the face. The gradient at the face is calculated using the compact stencil formulation [72].

In the case where the discretisation takes place at the orifice nodes, Equation (3.12) is used to calculate the viscous losses through the orifice. Therefore, the diffusion contribution

at the faces connecting any two orifice nodes (e.g. the face connecting O_A and O_B or O_A and O_{C1} on the right-hand side of Figure 4.1) is replaced with the empirical loss term. For flow within the orifice shown on the right-hand side of Figure 4.1, the diffusive term at the orifice node, O_A , is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) = \frac{1}{V_{O_A}} \left(\mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) \cdot \mathbf{\Gamma} \Big|_{f_{G-O_A}} \right. \\ \left. + \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) \cdot \mathbf{\Gamma} \Big|_{f_{D-O_A}} \right. \\ \left. + \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) \cdot \mathbf{\Gamma} \Big|_{f_{P-O_A}} \right. \\ \left. - V_{O_A} \frac{C \rho \tilde{u}_O^2}{L} \mathbf{n}_O \right), \end{aligned} \quad (4.12)$$

where the subscript f_{G-O_A} , for example, refers to the face connecting nodes G and O_A . Note that the empirical loss term accounts for the contributions of the faces connecting O_{C1} , O_{C2} and O_B to O_A . In a general case, the diffusion contribution for any orifice node is written as

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) = \frac{1}{V_{O_i}} \left(\sum_{f \in A_{O_i}} (\mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) (H_O - 1) \cdot \mathbf{\Gamma}) \Big|_f \right. \\ \left. - V_{O_i} \frac{C \rho \tilde{u}_O^2}{L} H_O \mathbf{n}_O \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4.13)$$

$$H_O = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if face, } f, \text{ connects two orifice nodes} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases},$$

where \mathbf{n}_O is a unit vector along the orifice in the direction of the flow.

4.3 Numerical Calculation of Loss Coefficient

The loss coefficient, C , in the discretised diffusion equation (4.13) can be determined using Equation (2.36), repeated here for readability:

$$C = \frac{\phi_{l0visc}^2 \frac{K_{f10} L}{D_H} + \phi_{l0cont}^2 K_{cont} + \phi_{l0exp}^2 K_{exp}}{2}.$$

Since only nodal values of the fluid and flow properties are known, some equations from Section 2.2 cannot be used directly. This section gives an overview of how the loss coefficient is determined numerically.

The volume flow rate of each phase in the orifice, \dot{V}_g and \dot{V}_l , is calculated, respectively, as

$$\dot{V}_g = \sum_{A_i} ((1 - \alpha_i)A(|\mathbf{u}|n_o))|_{A_i} \quad (4.14)$$

and

$$\dot{V}_l = \sum_{A_i} (\alpha_i A(|\mathbf{u}|n_o))|_{A_i} , \quad (4.15)$$

where A_i is the area of each of the faces connecting orifice nodes from opposite sides, α_i is the Volume-Of-Fluid (4.2) of the cells adjacent to A_i filled with liquid and \mathbf{n}_o is a unit normal along the orifice in the direction of the flow. The dryness fraction and mass velocity from Equations (2.23) and (2.25) is calculated numerically as

$$x = \frac{\rho_g \dot{V}_g}{\rho_l \dot{V}_l + \rho_g \dot{V}_g} \quad (4.16)$$

and

$$G = \frac{\rho_l \dot{V}_l + \rho_g \dot{V}_g}{A} , \quad (4.17)$$

respectively.

The friction loss coefficient, K_{f10} , is calculated using Equation (2.5) where the Reynolds number is determined from the mixture mass velocity, G , and the liquid viscosity, μ_l . The expansion and contraction loss coefficients are given in Equations (2.12) and (2.16), respectively, where σ_c is given as a user input and can be determined using Equation (2.18). Finally, the two-phase multipliers in Equation (2.36) are calculated using Equations (2.26), (2.33) and (2.34).

4.4 VOF Advection for Orifice Elements

In this section a modification to the discretisation of the VOF equation for orifice cells will be explained. The CICSAM method [70] is used to discretise the volume fraction equation (4.1) and calculate the advection of α between neighbouring nodes. An assumption in the method is that the computational nodes are located at the centroids of the cells (finite volumes). This has a direct influence on the inter-nodal distances, which is a parameter required in the calculation. Since there is a large amount of anisotropy introduced in the mesh by orifice cells which can be much larger than neighbouring cells, there is often a large deviation between

the finite volume centroid position and the vertex centered node's location inside the cell. Figure 4.2 shows orifice element cells with nodes at x_2 and x_3 along with standard finite volume cells with nodes at x_1 and x_4 . The centroids of the orifice element cells, indicated with the \times 's, are positioned at x_2^* and x_3^* . Therefore, for CICSAM to work with the one-dimensional orifice element model, the positions of the centroids of the orifice element cells (x_2^* and x_3^*) are used instead of the nodal positions of those cells (x_2 and x_3) to calculate the distance between two adjacent cells.

Figure 4.2: Nodes in orifice region (x_1 to x_4) with their cell volumes where the \times 's indicate the actual centroid of the cell volume.

This modification was introduced into the ELEMENTAL[®] code for all orifice cells. The effect of this adjustment will be shown in the numerical test case in Section 5.5. In the next chapter some cases will be presented as validation tests for all the additions made to the code for orifice elements.

Chapter 5

Validation of One-Dimensional Orifice Elements

The one-dimensional orifice elements have been implemented into the ELEMENTAL[®] code. The finite volume discretisation of the one-dimensional orifice elements is validated in this chapter. Note that analytical and empirical models of the loss coefficient, C , that apply directly to the test cases are used instead of Equation (2.36). This is due to the test cases not resembling orifice geometries, but rather geometries where the flow can be determined analytically or compared directly to experimental results. In Chapter 6, the discretisation of the one-dimensional orifice elements along with Equation (2.36), which is used to determine the loss coefficient, will be validated.

5.1 Plane Poiseuille Flow

The numerical discretisation of the one-dimensional orifice elements in a two-dimensional domain is validated here by modelling plane Poiseuille flow. A two-dimensional channel with height, h , containing a fluid with density, ρ , and viscosity, μ , is shown below. The channel walls are stationary and a body force acceleration, \mathbf{a} , is acting on the fluid.

Figure 5.1: Plane Poiseuille flow.

If the flow is driven by acceleration alone, is fully developed and laminar ($Re < 2100$), the velocity as a function of the vertical height can be found analytically using Equation (3.5)

$$u(y) = -\frac{a_x}{2\mu} \left(y^2 - \frac{h^2}{4} \right) \quad (5.1)$$

and the average velocity, \tilde{u} , over a cross-section

$$\tilde{u} = \frac{a_x}{12\mu} h^2. \quad (5.2)$$

Combining Equations (3.13) and (5.2) gives

$$a_x = \frac{12\mu}{h^2} \tilde{u} = \frac{C(\tilde{u})\rho\tilde{u}^2}{L}, \quad (5.3)$$

where the loss coefficient, $C(\tilde{u})$, can be solved such that

$$C(\tilde{u}) = \frac{12\mu L}{h^2 \rho} \frac{1}{\tilde{u}}. \quad (5.4)$$

A two-dimensional numerical simulation of flow through a channel section is conducted in ELEMENTAL[®] using the one-dimensional orifice element model. A large portion of the small elements in the mesh is replaced with long one-dimensional orifice elements shown in Figure 5.2. The orifice elements in the channel is given length, $L = 0.5$ m, and height, $h = 0.5$ m, and the fluid is given density, $\rho = 1$ kg/m³, and viscosity, $\mu = 1$ Ns/m². A body acceleration in the x -direction, $a_x = -48$ m/s², is prescribed. The resulting Reynolds number for these parameters is exactly 0.5 and the flow is therefore laminar. The left and right boundaries are given periodic boundary conditions such that the flow properties at both the inlet and outflow boundaries are the same.

The velocity magnitude colour map is shown in Figure 5.3. The velocity profile at both the one-dimensional element region and the full resolution region is compared to the analytical solution in Figure 5.4. The L2-norm error is given by

$$\|e\|_{L_2} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{n_{nodes}} (u_a - u_n)^2}, \quad (5.5)$$

where n_{nodes} is the number of nodes on the inflow cross-section of the orifice and u_a and u_n are, respectively, the analytical and numerical velocity. The L2-norm error of the velocity profile in the one-dimensional element region and the full resolution region is $2.96e-12$ and $1.76e-12$, respectively, which validates the numerical discretisation of the one-dimensional orifice elements in a two-dimensional domain. Theoretically, the pressure field within the channel is constant and in the simulation, a constant pressure field was also obtained with a maximum pressure deviation of $1.6e-10 Pa$.

Figure 5.2: Mesh used in Plane Poiseuille flow test case.

Figure 5.3: Mesh and velocity profile of Plane Poiseuille flow test case.

Figure 5.4: Velocity as a function of height at both the full resolution and one-dimensional element region of Plane Poiseuille flow test case.

5.2 Hagen-Poiseuille Flow

The numerical discretisation of the one-dimensional orifice elements in a three-dimensional domain is now validated by modelling Hagen-Poiseuille flow. A three-dimensional circular channel, or pipe, with radius, R , containing a fluid with density, ρ , and viscosity, μ , is shown below. The channel walls are stationary and a body force acceleration, \mathbf{a} , is acting on the fluid.

Figure 5.5: Hagen Poiseuille flow.

If the flow is driven by acceleration alone, is fully developed and laminar ($Re < 2100$), the velocity as a function of the radius can be shown to be

$$u(r) = \frac{1}{4\mu} a_x (r^2 - R^2) \quad (5.6)$$

and the average velocity, \tilde{u} , over a cross-section

$$\tilde{u} = \frac{1}{8\mu} a_x R^2. \quad (5.7)$$

Combining Equations (3.13) and (5.7) gives

$$a_x = \frac{8\mu}{R^2} \tilde{u} = \frac{C(\tilde{u})\rho\tilde{u}^2}{L} \quad (5.8)$$

and the loss coefficient, $C(\tilde{u})$, can be solved such that

$$C(\tilde{u}) = \frac{8\mu L}{R^2 \rho} \frac{1}{\tilde{u}}. \quad (5.9)$$

A three-dimensional numerical simulation of flow through a circular channel is conducted in ELEMENTAL[®] using the one-dimensional orifice model. A portion of the small elements in the mesh is replaced with long one-dimensional elements shown in Figure 5.6. The orifice elements in the channel is given length, $L = 0.5$ m, and radius, $R = 0.5$ m and the fluid is given density, $\rho = 1$ kg/m³, and viscosity, $\mu = 0.1$ Ns/m². A body acceleration in the x -direction, $a_x = -40$ m/s², is prescribed. The resulting Reynolds number for these parameters is exactly 1 and the flow is therefore laminar. The left and right boundaries are given periodic boundary conditions such that the flow properties at both the inlet and outflow boundaries are the same.

A velocity magnitude colour map at a cross-section in the one-dimensional element region of the channel is shown in Figure 5.7. No observable difference between the flow profile in the one-dimensional element region and the full resolution region was observed. The graph in Figure 5.8 shows the velocities as a function of the radius at both the one-dimensional element and full resolution regions. The L2-norm error of the velocity (5.5) in the one-dimensional element and full resolution region are both 6.32e-6, which validates the numerical discretisation of the one-dimensional orifice elements in a three-dimensional domain. Theoretically, the pressure field within the channel is constant and in the simulation, a constant pressure field was also obtained with a maximum pressure deviation of 3.19e-13 Pa. Next, the ability

of the one-dimensional orifice elements along with empirical correlations to determine the loss coefficient in transient simulations is assessed.

Figure 5.6: Mesh used in Hagen Poiseuille flow test case.

Figure 5.7: Velocity contour plot over cross-section of channel of Hagen Poiseuille flow test case.

Figure 5.8: Velocity as a function of height at both the full resolution and one-dimensional element region of the Hagen Poiseuille flow test case.

5.3 Two-Dimensional Reservoir Test Case

The ability of the one-dimensional orifice elements to calculate the flow velocity in a two-dimensional transient simulation (using empirical correlations to calculate the loss coefficient) is now assessed. A two-dimensional reservoir system, shown in Figure 5.9, contains two fluids. The reservoirs are connected via two-dimensional channels with lengths and heights of 9.5 m and 0.5 m, respectively, at both the top and the bottom to allow fluid to move from one reservoir to the other due the effects of gravity. The bottom and top fluids have densities 100 kg/m^3 and 1 kg/m^3 , respectively. Both fluids have a viscosity of 1 Ns/m^2 to ensure laminar flow, with the maximum Reynolds number achieved in the simulation $Re = 26$.

Figure 5.9: 2D Reservoir system with two fluids (left) with full resolution mesh (top right) and mesh with 1D elements (bottom right).

The flow rate from the one reservoir to the other is first measured numerically with a full resolution simulation (mesh shown on the top right of Figure 5.9). The flow rate is then compared to that obtained by a simulation using the one-dimensional orifice element model, with the mesh similar outside of the orifice elements. Inside the channel, the mesh is replaced with larger one-dimensional orifice elements (bottom right of Figure 5.9) in which the viscous losses are modelled. The loss coefficient for the one-dimensional elements is calculated using empirical correlations from Chen [53] as

$$C(\tilde{u}) = \frac{12\mu L}{h^2\rho} \frac{1}{\tilde{u}} + \frac{K_i}{2} \frac{1}{\tilde{u}} \quad (5.10)$$

$$K_i = 1.2 + \frac{38}{Re}.$$

Note that the inlet loss coefficient, K_i , is included here since the maximum flow development length, L' (2.7), is 0.83 m indicating that the flow develops fully within the channel.

Figure 5.10 shows that the flow rate over time for both simulations are in good agreement. There are some error in the one-dimensional orifice element model simulation which can be

due to a combination of the error in Equation (5.10) as well as the error in the flow profile which is not uniform along the channel due developing flow. The results does however confirm that the one-dimensional orifice element model is applicable to transient simulations where the flow velocity can fluctuate as well as reverse in direction.

Figure 5.10: Flow rate through channel of 2D reservoir test case.

5.4 Three-Dimensional Reservoir Test Case

The ability of the one-dimensional orifice elements to calculate the flow velocity in a three-dimensional transient simulation (using empirical correlations to calculate the loss coefficient) is now assessed. A three-dimensional reservoir system, shown below, contains two fluids. The reservoirs are connected via circular cross-section channels at both the top and the bottom to allow fluid to move from one reservoir to the other due the effects of gravity. The bottom channel has length 8 m and diameter 0.5 m. The bottom and top fluids have densities 100 kg/m^3 and 1 kg/m^3 , respectively. Both fluids have a viscosity of 1 Ns/m^2 to ensure laminar flow with the maximum Reynolds number achieved in the simulation, $Re = 30$.

Figure 5.11: 3D Reservoir system with two fluids (left) with full resolution mesh (top right) and mesh with 1D elements (bottom right).

The flow rate from the one reservoir to the other is first measured numerically with a full resolution simulation (mesh shown on the top right of Figure 5.11). The flow rate is then compared to that obtained by a simulation using the one-dimensional orifice element model, with the mesh similar outside of the orifice. Inside the channel, the mesh is replaced with larger one-dimensional orifice elements (bottom right of Figure 5.11) in which the viscous losses are modelled. The loss coefficient for the one-dimensional elements is calculated using empirical correlations from Chen [53] as

$$C(\tilde{u}) = \frac{8\mu L}{R^2 \rho \tilde{u}} + \frac{K}{2} \frac{1}{\tilde{u}} \quad (5.11)$$

$$K = 1.2 + \frac{38}{Re}.$$

Note again that the inlet loss coefficient, K_i , is included here since the maximum flow development length, L' (2.7), is 0.95 m indicating that the flow develops fully within the channel.

Figure 5.12 shows the flow rate over time for both simulations are in good agreement. The error in the one-dimensional orifice element model simulation can again be due to a combination of the error in Equation (5.11) as well as the error in the flow profile which is not uniform along the channel due developing flow. The results does however confirm that

the one-dimensional orifice element model is applicable to transient simulations in a three-dimensional domain where the flow velocity can fluctuate as well as reverse in direction. Next, the discretisation of the VOF equation will be validated.

Figure 5.12: Flow rate through channel of 3D reservoir test case.

5.5 Two-phase Interface Test Case

To ensure the correct discretisation of the VOF advection term using the CICSAM scheme (as explained in Section 4.4), a test is performed where a step function in the VOF field is advected through a channel containing orifice elements. A block of fluid, Fluid 1, shown in Figure 5.13, flows in a two-dimensional channel and is surrounded by another fluid, Fluid 0. The fluids both move at a constant velocity of 1 m/s through the channel. Both fluids are modelled as inviscid and it is therefore expected that the interface between the two fluids stays sharp and does not smear as it travels along the channel. The mesh in Figure 5.2 is used for this simulation. The results in Figure 5.14 shows the fluid interface before and after it had travelled through the one-dimensional orifice elements, both with and without the changes made to accommodate CICSAM as explained in Section 4.4. It can be seen that the interface smears while passing through the one-dimensional orifice elements without the changes to CICSAM. With the modification applied, however, it stays sharp and matches

the expected position of the block of fluid after the orifice section. The analytical solution of the interface position at the different times is shown by the white dotted lines in Figure 5.14.

Figure 5.13: Sharp fluid interface test case.

Figure 5.14: Fluid interface plot before Fluid 1 (red) travelled through the one-dimensional orifice elements (top). Fluid interface plot after Fluid 1 (red) travelled through the one-dimensional orifice elements with (bottom) and without (middle) the changes to CICSAM.

The one-dimensional orifice elements are not expected to smear an interface parallel with the orifice flow direction. This is due to the orifice element nodes being positioned at the centre of the element in the direction normal to the orifice flow. It was tested and found to behave as expected.

Chapter 6

Violent Slosh Test Case Results

A laboratory experiment of violent sloshing in a partially filled tank was conducted. The tank is divided into halves by baffles shown in Figure 6.1. These baffles form orifices within the tank. Significant pressure losses may occur when fluid moves from one compartment to the other. The tank was subjected to a sinusoidal acceleration in the x -direction (Figure 6.1) during the experiments and the pressure at points p_1 and p_2 in the tank were measured and reported. 2D CFD simulations using ELEMENTAL[®] (both with and without the one-dimensional orifice elements) of the same tank with the same acceleration and fill level were conducted and the results compared to experimental measurements. The experimental results are confidential and therefore time and pressure differences values are normalized with their respective maximum values.

Figure 6.1: Cross-section of tank showing position of baffles and pressure sensors of violent slosh test case.

6.1 Full Resolution Simulation Results

A numerical simulation of the experiment is done with ELEMENTAL[®]. The computational mesh is shown in Figure 6.2. Note the relatively small computational element sizes in the orifices. The experimental and numerical pressure differences, $p_1 - p_2$, are compared in Figures 6.3 and 6.4 and are in very good agreement. Figure 6.5 shows the local Reynolds numbers of the flow within the respective orifices over time. The Reynolds number is calculated with the velocity being the average velocity in the orifice and the length scale being the height of the orifice. It can be seen that the flow through the orifices switch between laminar and turbulent flow.

Figure 6.2: Full resolution computational mesh of violent slosh test case.

Figure 6.3: Comparison of full resolution numerical and experimental pressure difference, $p_1 - p_2$, of violent slosh test case.

Figure 6.4: Enlarged comparison of full resolution numerical and experimental pressure difference, $p_1 - p_2$, of violent slosh test case.

Figure 6.5: Reynolds number of flow in each orifice over time of violent slosh test case.

6.2 Results using 1D Orifice Element Model

The results for cases where the computational elements in the orifices are replaced with one-dimensional orifice elements are presented now. Three different computational meshes are used and shown in Figure 6.6 with zoomed in images of the mesh around the orifice areas shown in Figure 6.7. Inside the orifices, the standard finite volume elements are replaced with the one-dimensional orifice elements. For the top orifice all three meshes have three orifice elements in the vertical direction, since the flow passage is very small. The difference between the meshes lies in the amount of orifice elements per orifice in the bottom and middle orifices which is summarised in Table 6.1.

	No. of Orifice Elements		
	Top Orifice	Middle Orifice	Bottom Orifice
Mesh A	3	7	8
Mesh B	3	4	4
Mesh C	3	3	3

Table 6.1: Number of one-dimensional orifice elements in each computational mesh.

Mesh A

Mesh B

Mesh C

Figure 6.6: Computational meshes for one-dimensional orifice element model simulations of violent slosh test case.

Figure 6.7: Computational meshes around orifices for one-dimensional orifice element model simulations of violent slosh test case.

The measured experimental as well as the numerically calculated full resolution simulation pressure difference, $p_1 - p_2$, are compared to that of the one-dimensional orifice element model simulations in Figures 6.8 and 6.9. The flow rate over time through each orifice in the one-dimensional element model is plotted and compared to the full resolution simulation results in Figures 6.10 to 6.12. The total mass in the left-hand side of the tank over time for each simulation is plotted in Figure 6.13. Additionally, the relative mass difference in the left-hand side of the tank of the one-dimensional element model simulations compared to the full resolution simulation, are shown in Figure 6.14 for Meshes A to C. Here the relative mass difference is given by $\frac{m_F - m_O}{m_F}$ where m_F and m_O are, respectively, the masses in the left-hand side of the tank calculated in the full resolution and one-dimensional orifice element model simulations.

Figure 6.8: Comparison of pressure difference, $p_1 - p_2$, of violent slosh test case.

Figure 6.9: Enlarged comparison of pressure difference, $p_1 - p_2$, of violent slosh test case.

Figure 6.10: Flow Rate through bottom orifice in violent slosh test case using one-dimensional orifice element model.

Figure 6.11: Flow Rate through middle orifice in violent slosh test case using one-dimensional orifice element model.

Figure 6.12: Flow Rate through top orifice in violent slosh test case using one-dimensional orifice element model.

Figure 6.13: Mass of fluid on left half of tank of violent slosh test case.

Figure 6.14: Relative mass difference in left-hand side of tank of one-dimensional orifice element model simulation to full resolution simulation of violent slosh test case.

Figures 6.8 and 6.9 show the pressure difference over the tank walls calculated using the one-dimensional orifice element model with each computational mesh. It can be seen that the results are in good agreement with both the experimental and full resolution numerical results over the full duration of the simulation. Another metric to consider when evaluating the one-dimensional orifice element model is the flow rates through the orifices.

The flow rates through the orifices (Figures 6.10 to 6.12) using the one-dimensional orifice element model for both Mesh A and Mesh B are in good agreement for at least the first 25% of the simulation. The flow rate using Mesh C is however slightly lower than expected. This may be due to the up- and downstream mesh element sizes which are much bigger compared to those in Mesh A and Mesh B. After the first 25% of simulation time, the difference in the flow rate of the one-dimensional orifice element model simulations compared to the full resolution simulation increases. This is largely due to the difference in the free surface, shown in Figure 6.15, towards the middle and end of the simulation as a result of differences in mesh resolution. Other factors such as the one-dimensional flow assumption within the orifices and the associated error of the one-dimensional orifice element model further increases the difference in flow rates.

Figure 6.15: Free surface of at time $\frac{t}{t_{max}} = 0.2$ on the full resolution mesh (top) and Mesh C (bottom) of violent slosh test case.

The total mass in the left half of the tank (Figures 6.13 and 6.14) is similar in the one-dimensional element model simulations and the full resolution simulation with a maximum relative difference of 3%. Therefore, the pressure difference over the tank, $p_1 - p_2$, using the one-dimensional element model is in very good agreement with the experimental results as shown in Figures 6.8 and 6.9.

The computational cost of the full resolution CFD simulation and the one-dimensional element model simulations are presented in Table 6.2. The one-dimensional element model requires less nodes in the computational mesh. Additionally, the model requires less time steps to complete the same simulation. This means that the overall time step sizes are bigger.

It is interesting to note that Meshes B and C require slightly more time steps than Mesh A, even though the majority of their mesh element sizes are much bigger. This can be attributed to the high flow velocities through the top orifice. The average velocity over time through the top orifice is 6 times the velocity through the middle and bottom orifice. All three meshes have similarly sized elements around the top orifice and therefore the time step sizes are limited by those elements. The full resolution mesh does not have the increased element sizes within the orifice which leads to the increased number of time steps for the full resolution simulation.

The one-dimensional element model simulations all require less time to complete the

	Full Resolution	1D Element Model		
		Mesh A	Mesh B	Mesh C
No of Nodes	3757	3458	3173	2263
No of Cores	1	1	1	1
CPU Time	67 786s	58 540s	46 892s	33 286s
Time Steps	154 606	129 170	131 062	130 958
Sim. speed, Z	8 569	7 632	8 868	8 903

Table 6.2: Comparison of computational cost of full resolution and one-dimensional element model simulations of violent slosh test case.

simulation compared to the full resolution simulation. There are also big differences in the simulation time for the one-dimensional element model simulations between the different meshes, with Mesh C having the smallest simulation time due the decrease in total number of nodes. A metric to determine the speed of a simulation for parallel processing is to measure the number of node-time steps per CPU second per core, which is defined as Z

$$Z = \frac{N_{nodes} \times N_{steps}}{t_{CPU} \times N_{cores}}. \quad (6.1)$$

This equation compares the computational efficiency between different simulations. The one-dimensional element model simulation using Mesh A has a slightly lower computational efficiency than the full resolution simulation, while the simulations on Meshes B and C both have a slightly higher computational efficiency. This shows that some efficiency is lost when using the one-dimensional element model if the number of nodes over the cross-sectional area of the orifices is not reduced.

In summary, the results show that the one-dimensional orifice element model reduces the accuracy of the calculated flow rates through the orifices (as a result of increased mesh element sizes up- and downstream of the orifices). The overall effect on the accuracy of the pressure difference over the tank walls, $p_1 - p_2$, is however small as shown in Figures 6.8 and 6.9. This is further illustrated by the maximum relative difference in the mass on the left-hand side of the tank using the one-dimensional element model compared to the full resolution simulation being less than 3%. The model does however significantly decrease computational time with up to a 50% reduction in CPU time using the one-dimensional orifice element model.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

7.1 Summary

In this work, a method to replace fine computational mesh elements within orifices with large one-dimensional elements are presented. The elements were shown to integrate seamlessly with standard finite volume elements for two-phase flow within accelerating reference frames in both two- and three-dimensions. Inside orifice volumes, one-dimensional elements are used to model the diffusion term of the momentum equation with a loss term instead of employing full finite volume discretisation. The loss term is based on existing semi-empirical models accounting for the fluid properties, flow conditions and orifice geometry.

As part of this work, the one-dimensional orifice element model was implemented in the finite volume code `ELEMENTAL`[®]. The implementation was validated using several test cases in both two- and three dimensions. These tests confirmed the correct implementation in code of the one-dimensional orifice elements. When the loss coefficient was determined from theory for a 2D laminar channel flow or for a pipe flow (Hagen-Poiseuille) problem, the losses matched theory to an accuracy limited by the numerical solver tolerance.

Further test cases which are transient and does not have analytical solutions, such as flow from one tank to another (Sections 5.3 and 5.4), were also conducted. Here the loss coefficient were estimated using empirical correlations. In these cases, the one-dimensional element model simulation results were in good agreement with the full resolution simulation results validating its ability to model transient flow using empirical correlations to determine the loss coefficient.

The test cases revealed that special consideration had to be taken while discretising the volume fraction equation, (4.1), to ensure that a sharp fluid interface is kept while it passes through an orifice. This is due to the nodes in the one-dimensional orifice elements not being at the centroid of the cells as required by the CICSAM method which is used to discretise the volume fraction equation. A modification to the code were made such that CICSAM uses the position of the centroid of the orifice element cells instead of the nodal positions. This modification was tested and proved to work.

The one-dimensional orifice elements were also tested in a violent sloshing simulation and compared to experimental and full resolution simulation results. The one-dimensional orifice element model decreases the simulation CPU time up to 50%. This is due to the one-dimensional orifice element model:

- reducing the total number of nodes,
- and increasing the time step sizes by increasing the element sizes in and around the orifices.

The overall coarser mesh resolution does however come at a cost to the accuracy of the flow rates within the orifices.

The proposed one-dimensional orifice elements are suitable for two-phase flow in accelerating reference frames for any two- and three-dimensional finite volume CFD solvers. The one-dimensional orifice elements in this work are however restricted to long orifices (where the orifice length is at least 1.4 times its diameter) with constant cross-sections. The performance of this model with different orifice length to diameter ratios needs to be investigated. Further investigation into the applicability of this model to orifices with varying cross-sectional areas are also required.

Bibliography

- [1] S. T. Golla and B. Venkatesham, “Experimental study on the effect of centrally positioned vertical baffles on sloshing noise in a rectangular tank,” *Applied Acoustics*, vol. 176, p. 107890, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0003682X20309944>
- [2] S. Zheng, F. Gao, Z. Zhang, H. Liu, and B. Li, “Topology optimization on fuel tank rib structures for fuel sloshing suppression based on hybrid fluid–solid SPH simulation,” *Thin-Walled Structures*, no. 165, 2021.
- [3] F. Gambioli and A. Malan, “Fuel loads in large civil airplanes,” *International Forum on Aeroelasticity and Structural Dynamics*, 2017.
- [4] F. Gambioli, R. Usach, J. Kirby, T. Wilson, and P. Behruzi, “Experimental evaluation of fuel sloshing effects on wing dynamics,” *International Forum on Aeroelasticity and Structural Dynamics*, 2019.
- [5] T. M. Barrows and J. S. Orr, “Chapter 3 - slosh modeling,” in *Dynamics and Simulation of Flexible Rockets*, T. M. Barrows and J. S. Orr, Eds. Academic Press, 2021, pp. 53–75. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B978012819994700008X>
- [6] J. Gerrits and A. Veldman, “Dynamics of liquid-filled spacecraft,” *Journal of Engineering Mathematics*, vol. 45, pp. 24–38, 2003.
- [7] G. S. Brar and S. Singh, “An experimental and cfd analysis of sloshing in a tanker,” *Procedia Technology*, vol. 14, pp. 490–496, 2014, 2nd International Conference on Innovations in Automation and Mechatronics Engineering, ICIAME 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S221201731400098X>

- [8] F. Gambioli, A. Chamos, S. Jones, P. Guthrie, J. Webb, J. Levenhagen, P. Behruzi, F. Mastroddi, A. Malan, S. Longshaw, A. Skillen, J. Cooper, L. González, and S. Marrone, “Sloshing wing dynamics -project overview,” 04 2020.
- [9] L. He, A. Zhao, Y. Li, B. Zhou, and W. Liang, “Effect of processing method on the spring-in of aircraft ribs,” *Composites Communications*, vol. 25, p. 100688, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2452213921000644>
- [10] J. D. P. Muñoz, “Fuel Sloshing effect on Dynamic Loads,” Master’s thesis, University Carlos III of Madrid, 2014.
- [11] H. Versteeg and W. Malalasekera, *An Introduction to Computational Fluid Dynamics: The Finite Volume Method*. New York, 1995. [Online]. Available: <https://books.google.co.za/books?id=uZBpQgAACAAJ>
- [12] C. Hirt and B. Nichols, “Volume of fluid (vof) method for the dynamics of free boundaries,” *Journal of Computational Physics*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 201–225, 1981. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0021999181901455>
- [13] T. Kandasamy, S. Rakheja, and A. Ahmed, “An Analysis of Baffles Designs for Limiting Fluid Slosh in Partly Filled Tank Trucks,” *The Open Transportation Journal*, no. 4, pp. 23–32, 2010.
- [14] L. Barcenasa, E. Ledesma-Orozcoa, S. Van-der Veenb, F. Reveles-Arredondoa, and E. A. Rodríguez-Sánchez, “An optimization of part distortion for a structural aircraft wing rib: an industrial work flow approach,” *CIRP Journal of Manufacturing Science and Technology*, no. 28, pp. 15–23, 2020.
- [15] R. Courant, K. Friedrichs, and H. Lewy, “On the partial difference equations of mathematical physics (translated from german),” *Inst. Math. Sci. New York Univ.*, 1956.
- [16] B. Thirunavukkarasu and T. K. R. Rajagopal, “Numerical investigation of sloshing in tank with horivert baffles under resonant excitation using cfd code,” *Thin-Walled Structures*, vol. 161, p. 107517, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0263823121000768>

- [17] V. Santhanam, “Slosh Damping with Floating Magnetoactive Micro-Baffles ,” Master’s thesis, Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University, 2014.
- [18] E. Demirel and M. M. Aral, “Liquid sloshing damping in an accelerated tank using a novel slot-baffle design,” *Water*, vol. 10, no. 11, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4441/10/11/1565>
- [19] M. H. Mubaroka, S. J. Zarrouka, and J. E. Cater, “Two-phase flow measurement of geothermal fluid using orifice plate: Field testing and CFD validation,” *Renewable Energy*, no. 134, pp. 927–946, 2019.
- [20] M. H. Mubaroka, J. E. Cater, and S. J. Zarrouka, “Comparative CFD modelling of pressure differential flow meters for measuring two-phase geothermal fluid flow,” *Geothermics*, no. 86, 2020.
- [21] K. T. Trinh, “On The Critical Reynolds Number For Transition From Laminar To Turbulent Flow,” pp. 1–39, 2010. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1007.0810>
- [22] A. F. Pearce, “Critical reynolds number for fully-developed turbulence in circular submerged water jets,” *Council for Scientific and Industrial Research, Report MEG 475*, 1966.
- [23] F. M. White, *Viscous Fluid Flow*, 3rd ed. Boston: McGraw Hill, 2006.
- [24] L. Davidson, *An Introduction to Turbulence Models*, 2003.
- [25] G. N. Coleman and R. D. Sandberg, “A primer on direct numerical simulation of turbulence - methods, procedures and guidelines,” University of Southampton, Southampton, Tech. Rep. June 2015, 2010. [Online]. Available: <http://eprints.soton.ac.uk/66182/>
- [26] G. Romano, “Large and small scales in a turbulent orifice round jet: Reynolds number effects and departures from isotropy,” *International Journal of Heat and Fluid Flow*, vol. 83, p. 108571, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0142727X19309439>
- [27] J. Smagorinsky, “General circulation experiments with the primitive equations,” *Monthly Weather Review*, pp. 99–164, 1963.

- [28] O. Reynolds, “On the dynamical theory of incompressible viscous fluids and the determination of the criterion. [abstract],” *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London*, vol. 56, pp. 40–45, 1894. [Online]. Available: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/115570>
- [29] S. Benhamadouche, M. Arenas, and W. J. Malouf, “Wall-resolved Large Eddy Simulation of a flow through a square-edged orifice in a round pipe at $Re = 25,000$,” *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, vol. 312, pp. 128–136, 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2016.09.010>
- [30] S. Vijiapurapu and J. Cui, “Performance of turbulence models for flows through rough pipes,” *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, vol. 34, pp. 1458–1466, 2010. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apm.2009.08.029>
- [31] F. H. J. Imada, F. Saltara, and J. L. Balino, “Numerical Determination of Discharge Coefficients of Orifice Plates and Nozzles,” *22nd International Congress of Mechanical Engineering (COBEM 2013)*, pp. 1755–1760, 2013.
- [32] M. A. Mehmood, M. A. Ibrahim, A. Ullah, and M. H. Inayat, “CFD study of pressure loss characteristics of multi-holed orifice plates using central composite design,” *Flow Measurement and Instrumentation*, vol. 70, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flowmeasinst.2019.101654>
- [33] M. S. Shah, J. B. Joshi, A. S. Kalsi, C. S. Prasad, and D. S. Shukla, “Analysis of flow through an orifice meter: CFD simulation,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 71, pp. 300–309, 2012. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2011.11.022>
- [34] K. Akselvoll and P. Moin, “Large eddy simulation of a backward facing step flow,” *Engineering Turbulence Modelling and Experiments 2*, 1993.
- [35] C. Ozhan, D. Fuster, and P. Da Costa, “Multi-scale flow simulation of automotive catalytic converters,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, no. 116, pp. 161–171, 2014.
- [36] S. Porter, J. Saul, S. Aleksandrova, H. Medina, and S. Benjamin, “Hybrid flow modelling approach applied to automotive catalysts,” *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, vol. 40, p. 8435–8445, 2016.

- [37] H. Jordaan, P. Stephan Heyns, and S. Hoseinzadeh, “Numerical Development of a Coupled One-Dimensional/Three-Dimensional Computational Fluid Dynamics Method for Thermal Analysis With Flow Maldistribution,” *Journal of Thermal Science and Engineering Applications*, vol. 13, no. 4, 01 2021, 041017. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4049040>
- [38] M. Reader-Harris, *Orifice Plates and Venturi Tubes*. Springer International Publishing Switzerland, 2015.
- [39] G. L. Morrison, R. E. Deotte, G. H. Nail, and D. L. Panak, “Mean velocity and turbulence fields inside a $\beta=0.50$ orifice flowmeter,” *AIChE Journal*, vol. 39, no. 5, pp. 745–756, 1993.
- [40] W. Archer, “Experimental determination of loss of head due to sudden enlargement in circular pipes,” *Trans. ASCE*, no. 76, pp. 999–1026, 1913.
- [41] D. S. Miller, *Internal flow systems*, 2nd ed. Bedford: BHRA, 1990.
- [42] F. M. White, *Fluid mechanics*, 4th ed., J. P. Holman and J. Lloyd, Eds. WCB/McGraw Hill, 2011.
- [43] P. J. Spaur, “Investigation of Discharge Coefficients for Irregular Orifices,” Master’s thesis, West Virginia University, 2011.
- [44] D. C. Rennels and H. M. Hudson, *Pipe Flow - A Practical and Comprehensive Guide*. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2012. [Online]. Available: www.wiley.com
- [45] F. Shan, Z. Liu, W. Liu, and Y. Tsuji, “Effects of the orifice to pipe diameter ratio on orifice flows,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 152, pp. 497–506, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0009250916303463>
- [46] D. Chisolm, *Two-phase Flow in Pipelines and Heat Exchangers*, 1st ed. New York: Longman Inc., 1983.
- [47] L. Moody, “Friction factors for pipe flow,” *Transactions of the ASME*, no. 66 (8), p. 671–684, 1944.
- [48] S. Churchill, “Friction-factor equation spans all fluid-flow regimes,” *Chemical Engineering*, no. 84, pp. 91–92, 1977.

- [49] N. Cheng, “Formulas for friction factor in transitional regimes,” *Journal of Hydraulic Engineering*, no. 134(9), pp. 1357–1362, 2008.
- [50] A. Avci and I. Karagoz, “A new explicit friction factor formula for laminar, transition and turbulent flows in smooth and rough pipes,” *European Journal of Mechanics / B Fluids*, no. 78, pp. 182–187, 2019.
- [51] G. Kojasoy, F. Landis, P. Kwame-Mensah, and C. T. Chang, “Two-phase pressure drop in multiple thick-and thin-orifice plates,” *Experimental Thermal and Fluid Science*, no. 55, pp. 347–358, 1997.
- [52] J. Douglas, J. Gasiorek, S. J.A., and J. L.B., *Fluid Mechanics*, 6th ed. England: Pearson Education Limited, 2011.
- [53] R. Chen, “Flow in the entrance region at low reynolds numbers,” *Journal of Fluid Engineering*, no. 95, pp. 153–158, 1973.
- [54] F. Anselmet, F. Ternat, M. Amielh, O. Boiron, P. Boyer, and L. Pietri, “Axial development of the mean flow in the entrance region of turbulent pipe and duct flows,” *Comptes Rendus Mécanique*, vol. 337, no. 8, pp. 573–584, 2009. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1631072109001090>
- [55] R. M. Sadri, “Channel Entrance Flow,” Master’s thesis, The University of Western Ontario, 1997.
- [56] W. Jianhua, A. Wanzheng, and Z. Qi, “Head loss coefficient of orifice plate energy dissipator,” *Journal of Hydraulic Research*, vol. 48, no. 4, pp. 525–530, 2010.
- [57] L. M. Milne-Thompson, *Theoretical Hydrodynamics*, 3rd ed. McMillan Co., 1957.
- [58] R. D. Grose, “Orifice contraction coefficient for inviscid incompressible flow,” *Journal of Fluids Engineering*, no. 107, pp. 36–43, 1985.
- [59] G. Belaud, L. Cassan, and J.-P. Baume, “Calculation of contraction coefficient under sluice gates and application to discharge measurement,” *Journal of Hydraulic Engineering*, vol. 135, no. 12, pp. 1086–1091, 2019.

- [60] M. K. Roul and S. K. Dash, "Single-phase and two-phase flow through thin and thick orifices in horizontal pipes," *Journal of Fluids Engineering, Transactions of the ASME*, vol. 134, pp. 1–14, 2012.
- [61] G. B. Wallis, *One-dimensional Two-phase Flow*, 1st ed. United States of America: McGraw-Hill, Inc., 1969.
- [62] R. Lockhart and R. Martinelli, "Proposed correlation of data for isothermal two-phase, two-component flow in pipes," *Chem. Eng. Progr.*, no. 45, pp. 19–48, 1949.
- [63] R. Martinelli and N. D.B., "Prediction of pressure drop during forced-circulation boiling of water," *Trans. ASME*, no. 70, pp. 695–702, 1948.
- [64] C. Baroczy, "A systematic correlation of two-phase pressure drop," *Chemical Engineering Progress Symposium Series*, no. 62(44), 1966.
- [65] D. Chisolm and L. Sutherland, "Prediction of pressure changes in pipeline systems during two-phase flow," *Paper 4 presented at Symposium on Fluid Mechanics and measurements on two-phase systems, University of Leeds*, 1969.
- [66] L. Friedel, "Mean void fraction and friction pressure drops: comparison of some correlations with experimental data," *European Two-Phase Flow Group Meeting, Grenoble*, 1977.
- [67] I. Neqton, I. B. Cohen, A. Whitman, and J. Budenz, *The Principia: The Authoritative Translation and Guide: Mathematical Principles of Natural Philosophy*, 1st ed. University of California Press, 1999. [Online]. Available: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.1525/j.ctv1xxshj>
- [68] J. Meriam and K. Kraig, *Engineering Mechanics Dynamics*, 7th ed. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2012.
- [69] G. Tryggvason, R. Scardovelli, and S. Zaleski, *Direct Numerical Simulations of Gas-Liquid Multiphase Flows*. Cambridge University Press, 2011.
- [70] O. Ubbink and R. I. Issa, "A method for capturing sharp fluid interfaces on arbitrary meshes," *Journal of Computational Physics*, vol. 153, pp. 26–50, 1999.

- [71] A. J. Chorin, “A numerical method for solving incompressible viscous flow problems,” *Journal of Computational Physics*, no. 135, pp. 118–125, 1967.
- [72] P. Crumpton, P. Moinier, and M. Giles, “An unstructured algorithm for high reynolds number flows on highly-stretched grids,” *Numerical methods in Laminar and Turbulent Flow*, 1997.